

Modelling Radicals in the Boundary Layer

Philip J. Jacobs, Nicola Carslaw, Dwayne E. Heard, Michael J. Pilling
School of Chemistry, University of Leeds,
Leeds LS2 9JT
UK
philipj@chem.leeds.ac.uk

Introduction

- ◆ The hydroxyl (OH) and hydroperoxy (HO₂) radicals are the principal radicals in tropospheric photochemical cycles
- ◆ The most important reactions controlling the concentrations of OH and HO₂ form the framework of this photochemical reaction zero-dimensional box model¹
- ◆ The model has been validated using results from two field campaigns

EASE '97 - Remote marine environment
AEROBIC '97 - Mountainous forested environment

Aims of the model

The principal aims are to :

- ◆ model field measurements of OH, HO₂ and Σ(HO₂+RO₂)

Radical measurement	Measurement technique
OH, HO ₂	Fluorescence assay by gas expansion (FAGE) ²
HO ₂ +RO ₂	Peroxy radical chemical amplification (PERCA) ³

- ◆ Understand the processes driving the chemistry :
 - ◆ by looking at the sources and sinks of radicals using a rate of production analysis (ROPA)
 - ◆ by using steady state expressions to calculate radical concentrations under clean conditions⁴

EASE '97

AEROBIC '97

- ◆ EASE '97 took place during May 1997
- ◆ The site is located on the western coast of Eire at the Mace Head Atmospheric Observatory
- ◆ The site experiences clean air ($\text{NO}_x \approx 50$ ppt) from the north-eastern Atlantic either from the north pole or from the USA. The focus here is on the polar air
- ◆ AEROBIC '97 took place during July and August 1997
- ◆ The site is located in the Rhodope mountains of north-western Greece, in a clearing of a fir tree forest at an altitude of 1100 m
- ◆ The site experiences semi-polluted air ($\text{NO}_x \approx 3$ ppb) with high biogenic alkene emissions from the vegetation

The following charts show the species responsible for OH loss during the two field campaigns

Species responsible for OH loss

The clean, polar conditions of EASE '97 demonstrate that CO and CH₄ are the primary species responsible for OH loss, together accounting for ~95% of total OH loss due to CO and NMHC

The forested conditions of AEROBIC'97 demonstrate high concentrations of biogenic alkenes such as isoprene and the monoterpenes, which together account for ~85% of total OH loss due to CO and NMHC

Model mechanism construction

- ◆ The hydrocarbon distribution was studied for each campaign
- ◆ A reactivity index for OH was calculated

$$\text{Reactivity} = k(\text{HC}_i) \times [\text{HC}_i]$$

- ◆ On this basis, the most important hydrocarbons were selected for inclusion in the model
- ◆ Each hydrocarbon degradation scheme was extracted from the MCM³
- ◆ Inorganic and heterogeneous chemistry were added to give overall mechanisms of 1450 reactions for EASE '97 and 1116 reactions for AEROBIC '97
- ◆ The model is constrained with field measurements of the longer-lived species from the field campaigns : radical concentrations are then predicted

OH modelling

EASE '97 averages for the polar air periods display that the model over predicts the measurements throughout the day by a factor of ~ 2 . It would appear that even for these clean conditions, some OH losses have not been included in the chemical scheme.

AEROBIC '97 campaign averages display that the model under predicts the measurements between 10:00 and 16:00. This discrepancy can be attributed to the sensitivity of modelled OH to possible uncertainties in measured isoprene.

HO₂+RO₂ modelling

- ◆ During EASE '97, there is good agreement between modelled and measured peroxy radical concentrations
- ◆ The model generally under predicts at night, indicating that a source(s) of radicals is absent from the model scheme
- ◆ Both model and measurements show $\Sigma(\text{HO}_2 + \text{RO}_2)$ concentrations reaching $\sim 3 \times 10^8$ molecule cm^{-3} at midday under these clean, polar air conditions

Rate of production analysis

The principal production and loss routes of OH during AEROBIC '97

Steady State Expression I

- ◆ Due to its short atmospheric lifetime ($\sim 1\text{s}$), OH reaches steady state very rapidly. At any time,

$$\text{Production of OH} = \text{Loss of OH}$$

- ◆ A **steady state expression** can be derived from a mechanism containing only 25 reactions and 17 species, which is able to describe clean air chemistry to the accuracy of the full model
- ◆ The expression involves production, termination and interconversion of OH and HO_2
- ◆ The steady state expression adopts the form of a cubic in HO_2^4
- ◆ The $\text{CH}_3\text{O}_2 + \text{HO}_2$ term was found to be insignificant when compared to loss due to reaction with NO, so it was removed from the algebraic expression, allowing the **cubic** to be simplified to a **quadratic**

Steady State Expression II

The quadratic adopts the form $\lambda x^2 + \mu x + \nu = 0$, where

- ◆ $\lambda = 2Bkt_2kp_4[CH_4] + 2Akt_1kp_5[NO] + Bkt_3kp_5[NO]$
- ◆ $\mu = 2J_1kt_2kp_4[CH_4] + Bkt[NO_2]kp_5[NO] + J_1kt_3kp_5[NO]$
- ◆ $\nu = J_1kt[NO_2]kp_5[NO] - (J_1 + J_2)Akp_5[NO]$

The cubic and quadratic expressions can reproduce full model $[HO_2]$ to within a 10% error under clean conditions

Conclusions

- ◆ Under clean, marine conditions, the model over predicts measurements of OH by a factor of 2. This may be due to OH losses not included in the model mechanism, e.g Loss of radicals due to aerosols formed on sea salt particles.
- ◆ Under forested conditions, OH loss is controlled by the reactive biogenic alkenes which, during AEROBIC '97, were present in high concentrations. An isoprene sensitivity study was carried out and modelled OH was found to be sensitive to its changes. The model under predicts OH measurements and this is thought to be due to the isoprene measurement uncertainties.
- ◆ Modelled and measured peroxy radicals agree very well during the day, but the model appears to under predict at night
- ◆ Under clean conditions, the full model predictions of OH and HO₂ can be approximated by cubic and quadratic expressions. These expressions will allow us to gain a clearer understanding of the processes taking place in the boundary layer.

References

- ◆ Carslaw et al.
- ◆ Creasey et al.
- ◆ Monks et al.
- ◆ N. Carslaw, P.J. Jacobs, M.J. Pilling, (1998)
- ◆ Jenkin et al. MCM (protocol paper)
- ◆ We would like to thank the BADC for compilation of all data from EASE '97 and to NERC for funding my Ph.D. We would also like to thank all ACSOE participants for the use of their data: Prof. S.A. Penkett, B. Bandy, S. Baugitte and Dr. L. Cardenas (University of East Anglia), Prof. P. Simmonds (University of Bristol), Dr. P. Monks (University of Leicester), Dr. D. Creasey, J. Lee, Dr. A. C. Lewis, J.B. McQuaid (University of Leeds). We particularly thank Dr. S.M. Saunders (University of Leeds), Drs. M.E. Jenkin and G.D. Hayman (AEAT plc, Culham) and Dr. R.G. Derwent (UK Met. Office, Bracknell) for help and advice with the model construction.